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DESIGN COLLABORATION IN MEDICAL RESEARCH

DESIGNING DOCTOR-PATIENT INTERACTION

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ABSTRACT

With the expansion of specialization has come a contraction of innovation needed to meet systemic problems. To rectify this, calls are coming for greater levels of collaboration across disciplines from research funding agencies such as the National Science Foundation (NSF) and National Institutes of Health (NIH). This paper describes the collaboration of graduate design students at the University of Cincinnati (UC) with researchers at Cincinnati Children's Hospital Medical Center (CCHMC) to improve doctor-parent interaction surrounding Attention-Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD). The combined CCHMC/UC team collaboratively designed communication materials to ensure 1) information provision on all treatment options and 2) elicitation of parent preferences among the treatment modalities. Preliminary testing of the materials has been encouraging. This paper reports on the collaborative design process of those materials.

Keywords: research, collaboration, research methods

INTRODUCTION

It is said that we know a lot more about less and less (Latterich, 2005). Ever narrowing disciplinary specialization has been accompanied by expansion in systemic problems that evade solution. In recognition of the need for comprehensive solutions, funding agencies such as the NSF and NIH increasingly call for collaboration in requests for proposals and program announcements in the sciences in general, and medicine in particular. Independent efforts have also been made to engage design in medicine to increase innovation. The Mayo Clinic formed the Center for

Innovation to integrate design and medical disciplines to facilitate change (Smith, 2010). The College of Design Architecture, Art, and Planning (DAAP) at the University of Cincinnati (UC) has collaborated in medical research since 2004 (Zender, 2006). If collaborative efforts such as those called for are to produce maximum results then models for collaboration across disciplines need to be described, evaluated, and refined. This paper offers a case study of a design and medical research collaboration.

SPECIFIC PROBLEM

Attention-Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) is a disorder characterized by symptoms of inattention, hyperactivity, and impulsiveness that cause impairment of academic, social, and family functioning. Based on recent estimates, 8.7% of school age children in the U.S. meet diagnostic criteria for ADHD (Froehlich, 2007). Increasingly, parents are seeking medical help and pursuing treatment for ADHD (Olfson, 2003).

Fortunately, there are three effective treatment options available: behavior therapy alone, medication alone, or behavior therapy and medication combined. With each option come a different palette of pros and cons. Among these medically reasonable alternatives, the best choice for an individual child depends on how the family values these pros and cons. This adds complexity to the decision-making process. The natural place for a parent to weigh this decision is through dialogue with their doctor who must present information on pros and cons for each treatment in a way that is easily understood, and elicit from families their values and preferences for the various options.

To improve doctor-parent interaction surrounding ADHD, Dr. William Brinkman and a team

at Cincinnati Children's Hospital Medical Center (CCHMC) initiated a research study funded by the CCHMC Place Outcomes Research Award. The study had three aims: 1) to describe doctor-parent interactions developing a treatment plan for children newly diagnosed with ADHD, 2) to implement and optimize a shared decision-making intervention through iterative cycles of use and refinement, and 3) estimate the effect of the intervention by comparing pre- and post-implementation encounters. 11 pediatricians from 7 community-based practices participated. Parents of children 6-10 years old being assessed for ADHD by these doctors were approached for participation. The study focused on this age range of children, because their parents would serve as the proxy decision makers. Doctor-parent encounters developing a treatment plan were video recorded. Parents completed surveys following the visits. Prior to implementing intervention materials, approximately 3 'usual care' encounters per doctor were video recorded.

By analyzing the video recorded doctor encounters with children newly diagnosed with ADHD, Dr. Brinkman's team found early in the study that doctor-parent discussions of treatment options tended to focus on medication (Brinkman et al., in press). None of the doctors framed the decision as an explicit choice between behavior therapy alone, medication alone, or combination of both. The decision at this first visit was focused on whether or not to start medications and, if so, which one. Parent involvement in selecting a medication was low despite the fact that stimulant medications can differ in ways that are important to families (e.g., duration, impact on daily routine, cost, etc.). In addition, doctors tended to give information more than they elicited parent values, preferences, or concerns. This suggested the need for a decision aid.

Patient decision aids have proven effective at both providing information and increasing doctor-patient interaction mainly in adult medical settings (O'Connor, 2009; Mullan, 2009). Standards have been developed to help ensure the quality of decision aids, including essential elements of the development process (Elwyn, 2006). Despite convincing evidence of effectiveness and explicit quality criteria, decision aids have been slow to be adopted in real-world practice settings (Gravel,

2006), particularly pediatrics. A group of researchers at the Mayo clinic, led by Victor Montori, MD, recognized the need to partner with experts in design to create innovative decision aids that were more likely to be used in real-world settings. The initial product from this collaboration was a set of interactive cards (Breslin, 2008) which were shown to dramatically increase patient involvement in selecting a diabetes medication that was a good fit based on the patient's preferences and lifestyle (Mullan, 2009). Discussions with Victor Montori and Maggie Breslin about their collaborative process prompted Dr. Brinkman to contact Professor Craig Vogel at the DAAP who provided an introduction to Professor Mike Zender and graduate students at UC.

DESIGN PROCESS

TEAM FORMATION AND COMMUNICATION

Based on the design support needs communicated by Dr. Brinkman and his team, Professor Zender formed a team of UC graduate design students to engage in the research and development of treatment decision aids for parents of children diagnosed with ADHD. Professor Zender selected graduate students who had a variety of design skill-sets and experiences. These skill-sets and experiences included specialization in: the development and design of health education materials, the design of print applications, user-centered research methodologies, and strategic design methodologies.

In order to establish project parameters, an initial meeting was conducted for both the CCHMC medical team members and UC design team members to introduce themselves and discuss the project objectives. During this initial meeting, both teams realized the need for partnership and collaboration. This preliminary discussion identified many opportunities for information visualization and interaction; however, neither team was able to clearly articulate what appropriate solutions were needed. As the discussion continued, it became apparent that both teams needed to work together to analyze the preliminary data and establish a structured work-flow model.

To help facilitate both analysis and work-flow, a structured method of communication was implemented. One team member from each team

was identified as the main point of contact. Lauren Rawe was selected as the CCHMC medical team representative and Marnie Meylor was selected as the UC design team representative. After exchanging contact information, these two team members were responsible for sending information to the partnering team, distributing received information to their own teams, facilitating questions, and scheduling meeting times/locations. This direct line of communication helped to further the collaboration process while ensuring consistent delivery of information.

PHASE I: PRE-INTERVENTION

Content

The collaborative work faced several challenges. First of all, design students needed to know and understand the relevant medical knowledge, which was completely new to them. Following the introductory meeting and after the design students received required training in protection of human subjects, the combined CCHMC/UC team met to review the medical team's initial findings and view selected videos of doctor-parent encounters. The combined team observed what had been tentatively described: a focus on medication with more doctor information provision and relatively less elicitation of parent preferences and concerns. Designers were initially puzzled why doctors focused solely on the medication option until the CCHMC medical team explained that doctors are trained primarily in medical, not behavioral interventions. Parent training in evidence-based behavioral interventions for ADHD are typically provided by psychologists, not pediatricians. Availability of these services varies, with waiting lists and out-of-pocket expenses seen as barriers. The observed emotional stress of parents accompanying ADHD children in the doctor meeting was discussed and a user profile described. This phenomenon is well described in the literature (Brinkman, 2009).

The combined team mutually agreed that parent communication materials had the capacity to address the observed problems through improved doctor-parent interaction and established the goal to collaboratively design communication materials to ensure 1) information provision on all treatment

options and 2) elicitation of parent preferences among the treatment modalities.

The CCHMC medical team presented a proposed information book containing all the content for design consideration. The UC design team initially evaluated the book content as too comprehensive and too detailed for the average parent. At this point the medical and design teams held several unstated expectations of each other. The medical team was unsure of the exact nature of the design team's contribution and felt the design team would make their proposed book content accessible to parents; the design team thought the medical team's content would have to be heavily edited and portions eliminated in order to succeed. The medical team did not expect the design team to advise on content issues, and the design team did not yet appreciate the importance or relevance of the content. There was potential for the medical team to doubt the ability of the design team to consult on content, and a converse potential for the design team to undervalue the medical team's ability to make communication decisions. Gaining trust took time and occurred step by step, and initial grants of trust were rewarded with prompt and reliable actions. One of the practical ways this occurred was through assigning mundane tasks such as making revisions and responding in a timely and accurate manner. Even showing up for meetings on time and holding meetings in each other's space helped build trust that empowered the project.

Problem framing and definition

After analyzing the preliminary data findings, observing video-recorded doctor-parent interactions, and reviewing the CCHMC medical team's proposed information book, the UC design team defined key project components to help establish testable design strategies. These key project components included: identifying key decisions makers, determining decision influences, developing family scenarios, evaluating the decision timeline, and creating a mind map of the content.

To start, the UC design team identified the key decision makers, also known as stakeholders. In regards to this project, key decision makers are defined as those who can affect or are affected by the actions of the greater whole. The decision

makers in this particular situation included the parents (as the proxy decision makers for their 6-10 year old child/patient) and the doctor. When designing materials to educate or create awareness, it was imperative for the combined CCHMC/UC team to understand the needs of these participants. For example, the team identified the need of the parents to be better informed of ADHD symptoms and classifications before attending the first meeting with the doctor.

In addition to identifying key decision makers, the team determined decision influences. These influences could either be based on personal interactions or home-life situations. The four main influencers the team determined included: teachers, extended family members/friends, financial status, and home/work pressures/obligations. Teachers have a direct relationship with the child and are often the first to recognize potential ADHD symptoms. They also help to inform the parents of potential ADHD resources (doctors, school psychologists, etc.). Extended family members/friends share personal accounts or relay second-hand stories, providing a perspective that is trusted by the parents. This can often lead to the communication of partial information or misinformation. Nonetheless, these accounts were observed to provide an initial starting point for the parents. The third influencer that contributes to the decision-making process is financial status, which can influence the parent's willingness to initiate treatment. And finally, home/work pressures/obligations affect the family. Some parents are limited by time constraints due to work schedules or family obligations. These constraints inhibit certain behavioral treatments and need to be considered when choosing an ADHD treatment modality.

Next, the UC design team developed four family scenarios based on the common observations from the doctor-parent video interactions. The first scenario identified parents that were open to all treatment options but had some reluctance about medication for a variety of reasons (e.g. influential family member or friend who didn't agree with using medicine, second hand information, fear of side effects, fear of negative impact on child's self-esteem). The second scenario identified parents who had previous experience with ADHD medication (e.g.

they were treated as a child or had another child currently or previously treated for ADHD) which could predispose parents either for or against various treatment options. The third scenario identified parents that were only interested in medications. This may have been driven by some parents feeling like they had exhausted behavioral approaches in the years leading up to their child being diagnosed with ADHD, and must resort to trying medication (Brinkman, 2009). The fourth scenario identified a minority of parents strongly opposed to medication because at least one parent didn't believe their child had a problem that required medical treatment.

In addition to these scenarios, the combined CCHMC/UC team identified a few other common observations that affected the decision-making process. These observations included the limited discussion between parent and doctor of behavioral treatments options. No physician presented ADHD treatment as an explicit choice between behavior therapy alone, medication alone, or both combined. Discussions about behavioral treatments were sometimes prompted by parents asking questions about them. One doctor provided an extensive tutorial on behavioral approaches for parents, but never asked whether parents were interested in learning or employing these approaches. More often, a doctor would make a comment like, 'you need to do all the behavioral things too' without explicit discussion of what the behavioral options were. When parents left the visit with a referral to a class to learn about evidence-based behavioral management strategies, it was often given only after parents had directly asked the doctor about the availability of such services. The study was limited to one visit per family, so it is impossible to know to what extent behavioral strategies had been discussed or implemented in the past. While children typically received the ADHD diagnosis at the visit we recorded, parents had likely been observing and attempting to modify the child's problem behaviors for years.

FOUR MOST COMMON FAMILY SCENARIOS

Figure 1. Scenarios and decision drivers

Finally, the team constructed a timeline to help better understand the opportunities and identify points to provide appropriate information delivery. The three main opportunities were identified as prior to the doctor encounter, during the doctor encounter, and post-doctor encounter. Considering these main opportunities, the UC design team evaluated the content from the CCHMC medical team's proposed information book using a mind map information display. The mind map detailed the content associated with each point on the timeline. The initial findings indicated that it was too much information to deliver during the doctor encounter and would overwhelm the parent. This particular realization led the team to develop a few concepts that would explore ways to inform and engage the parent throughout the decision-making process.

PHASE II: FIRST INTERVENTION: BROCHURES, WORKSHEET, CARDS

Once the combined CCHMC/UC team defined the key project components, project objectives and testable design strategies were developed. The project objectives included the following:

- increase the percentage of parents who are well informed about ADHD,
- communicate the three ADHD treatment modalities (behavior therapy, medicine, or

combination of both) and watchful waiting (no treatment but continued active monitoring of outcomes) as legitimate options, establish decisions as choice among options, increase the parents involvement in the decision-making process, increase the percentage of parents making a choice congruent with their values, and help parents understand the value of their decision.

Correlating the strategy components with the project objectives, the UC design team developed a series of information materials. Utilizing the encounters described in the decision timeline, the team created three different information delivery applications designed to work together in a system: a brochure, a worksheet and interactive cards (see Figure 2).

The time prior to the doctor encounter was identified as an opportunity to provide the parent with information about ADHD in the form of a brochure and a worksheet. The brochure addressed common questions often asked by parents and introduced the four ADHD treatment options. This brochure was prototyped in two forms: long brochure with comprehensive information, and short brochure with abbreviated content. In addition to the brochure, the worksheet was intended to encourage active participation of the parents by eliciting

DECISION TIMELINE

Figure 2. Phase II decision timeline is shown with design prototypes for each stage of the timeline for Phase II. Parent was instructed to bring the worksheet to the appointment with the doctor.

treatment goals and preferences. The worksheet posed questions that the parent might not otherwise consider and help better prepare them for the doctor encounter. The worksheet was intended to be given to the doctor at the encounter to help ensure that the doctor was aware of the parent’s preferences and help set the agenda for the visit. Early in the development process the decision was made to incorporate the short brochure with the worksheet. This was considered by the team to be the bare minimum amount of information that all parents needed to prepare them for the visit with their child’s doctor. All parents also received the long brochure to ensure that parents seeking more detailed information had access to this as well.

In addition to the brochure and worksheet, a series of interactive cards were developed to clearly and concisely outline the important information points that should be considered during the decision-making doctor-parent encounter. Cards to facilitate doctor-parent interaction had been considered from the outset by the CCHMC medical team based on the successful use of cards to stimulate discussion on diabetes treatment at the Mayo Clinic (Breslin, Mullan, & Montori, 2008). The diabetes cards had proven useful in facilitating the doctor-patient

interaction and aided patients in determining the best course of action that fit their needs. The CCHMC medical team chose card content for parents of children with ADHD, including: medication benefit, medication side-effects, medication duration, medication daily routine, medication costs, and behavioral treatment resources. In addition to reviewing the cards during the visit with their child’s doctor, parents took them home with them for reference following the encounter.

Utilizing the various strategic design concepts, the CCHMC medical team began implementing and testing the design solutions in doctor-parent encounters. Six parents received the brochure & worksheet, and were asked to read and complete these materials. Careful consideration was paid to determine which applications were most effective in these real-life situations. Success criteria were 1) increased parent knowledge of options and realistic outcome expectations, and 2) increased parent involvement in decision-making process.

Figure 3. Phase III decision timeline is shown with design prototypes for each stage of the timeline for Phase III. Parent was instructed to complete and bring the cards to the appointment with the doctor.

PHASE III: SECOND INTERVENTION: INTEGRATED CARDS

As Phase II materials were introduced and the doctor-parent encounter observed, these findings were combined with feedback and suggestions offered by doctors and brought back to the combined CCHMC/UC team for discussion to refine design applications. Frequent meetings allowed for open discussion of the rationale behind design and content decisions and ensured that the products were informed by the expertise of all team members. The CCHMC medical team observed that using two design formats (worksheet and cards) within the clinical visit was inefficient and posed a challenge for doctors. Review of videos showed that doctors literally had their hands full, juggling both the worksheet and cards. Often, there was not enough time for the doctor to address the activities the parent completed on the worksheet and also engage in the interactive card exercise. Physicians were also observed not asking parents to choose a card based on their concerns and values. The combined team realized the need to integrate design materials

through further revisions. The UC design team created new visual prototypes to further improve doctor-parent interaction. Various design ideas were initiated in this process, including forms as foldable post, portable booklet, portfolio with separated sheets, and information cards. In addition to different formats, different kinds of information and various combinations of information visualization were tried. The combined CCHMC/UC team met and evaluated the strengths and weaknesses of each at addressing observed shortcomings of previous material. Each proposal had its own uniqueness, and when gathered together, many good features were shared and utilized to update the previous design versions. During this iterative design process participated in by the entire team, the combined short brochure with integrated worksheet became a series of cards.

Considering factors such as convenience, flexibility, and cost, the team decided to adopt a card system as the final product format, which included a set of parent information cards with material adapted from the worksheet and a set of doctor cards (see Figure 3). A long brochure was retained as medical support material to provide

more integrated and comprehensive information. The medical team reviewed the content of all materials to ensure they remained at an appropriate reading level. At the end of this development process the design team revised their work several times changing font size, adjusting color, adding graphic icons, and making the whole design more systematic. Seven parents received early versions of the parent cards and a brochure.

Throughout this iterative design process, the CCHMC medical team implemented and tested the design solutions in doctor-parent encounters (see Figure 4). Parents were asked to read and complete the cards at a minimum and were provided the long booklet to read if they were motivated to explore topics in greater detail. After the first revised design

3. MEDICATION TREATMENT

INTRODUCTION

This is an active treatment that uses drug therapy to control ADHD symptoms.

- Parts of the brain help children pay attention. Medicine for ADHD works by helping the brain send messages to these parts of the brain. This helps children to pay attention.
- There are two types of medicines that can be used. One type is called stimulants and the second is called non-stimulants. Stimulant medicines are often tried first. In studies, more children benefit from stimulant medicines than non-stimulant medicines.
- Unlike other medicines, the right amount of ADHD medicine is not based only on your child's weight. Instead, you must work with your child's doctor to try a range of doses (lower, medium, higher) and see how your child responds. You and your child's teacher will need to watch your child closely and complete evaluation forms. You will also need to stay in close contact with the doctor's office through follow-up calls and visits.

BENEFIT

Here is our best guess of what will happen to 100 children with ADHD if they get medication treatment alone for 14 months.

	<p>56 Number who have self-control and focus as well as the average child their age who doesn't have ADHD</p>
	<p>44 Number who don't improve to that level</p>

DOWNSIDES

- Medicine costs money.
- Your child may have side effects. These are usually minor and decrease as a child gets used to the medicine. Side effects include:
 - Most common:** Decreased appetite, Trouble falling asleep, Stomach aches, Headaches, Increased crabbiness, Social withdrawal, Anxiety and/or crying. Some children are more active or get in a bad mood when the medicine is wearing off.
 - Less common:** Tics (i.e. muscle twitches, movements, or unusual vocal sounds that a child can't control).
 - Rare:** Increased heart rate and/or blood pressure, Growth delay, Hallucinations.

Talk with your doctor to discuss these side effects in more detail.

Updated: 02/10/2011

Figure 4. Sample information card.

draft came out, the medical team collected feedback from doctors about the cards and asked designers to make changes accordingly, such as the offer of a reference list, revision of potentially confusing words, and changes to ease readability, such as font size, colors, and image adjustments. Ten parents received parent cards and the long brochure containing these changes.

GOALS / PREFERENCES

PLEASE REMEMBER TO FILL OUT THIS WORKSHEET AND BRING IT TO YOUR CHILD'S NEXT APPOINTMENT.

To get started, please complete the following sentences regarding you and your child's treatment goals.

What would you like to see change? _____

What would your child like to see change? _____

Please answer the following questions about pre-existing heart problems.

Does your child have a history of...	Does anyone in your family have a history of...
Heart disease?..... <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Sudden death in children or young adults?..... <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Palpitations or feeling your heart flutter?..... <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Hypertrophic Cardiomyopathy?..... <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Passing out?..... <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Long QT syndrome?..... <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Seizures?..... <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	

What do you like most and least about each treatment option?

	Most	Least
Watchful Waiting	_____	_____
Behavioral Treatment	_____	_____
Medication Treatment	_____	_____
Combined Treatment	_____	_____

Please check all the options you want to discuss with your child's doctor.

<input type="checkbox"/> Watchful waiting	Please fill out the box below
<input type="checkbox"/> Try a behavioral treatment	Please fill out the orange card (behavioral treatment)
<input type="checkbox"/> Try a medication treatment	Please fill out the blue card (medication treatment)

WATCHFUL WAITING

IF YOU ARE INTERESTED IN TRYING WATCHFUL WAITING...

What problems or behaviors will you watch for? _____

How do you know when to try an active treatment? _____

Updated: 02/10/2011

Figure 5. Sample goals card.

PRELIMINARY FINDINGS

Preliminary testing of the materials has been encouraging. Parents have consistently completed the preference elicitation exercises designed to help set the agenda for discussion with their child's

DAILY ROUTINE			
DOES MY CHILD NEED TO SWALLOW A PILL?			
Medication	Times / day	When Taken	Method
METHYLPHENIDATES			
Ritalin	2 – 3 / day		Swallow whole or CRUSH to put in food
Metadate CD	1 / day	45 minutes before class or activity	Swallow, or sprinkle in applesauce, pudding, or yogurt
Concerta	1 / day	90 minutes before class or activity	Swallow ONLY
Ritalin LA	1 / day	45 minutes before class or activity	Swallow, or sprinkle in applesauce, pudding, or yogurt
Focalin	2 – 3 / day		Swallow whole or CRUSH to put in food
Focalin XR	1 / day	45 minutes before class or activity	Swallow, or sprinkle in applesauce, pudding, or yogurt
Daytrana (Methylphenidate patch)	1 / day	2 hours before class or activity, lasts 3 hours after removal	Patch
AMPHETAMINE SALTS			
Dexedrine	2-3 / day		Swallow whole or CRUSH to put in food
Adderall	2-3 / day		Swallow whole or CRUSH to put in food
Dexedrine Spansule	1 / day	AM 60 minutes before class or activity	Swallow ONLY
Adderall XR	1 / day	45 minutes before class or activity	Swallow, or sprinkle in applesauce, pudding, or yogurt
Vyvanse	1 / day	60 minutes before class or activity	Swallow, or dissolve in applesauce, pudding,
ATOMOXETINE			
Strattera	1 / day	*	Swallow
GUANFACINE			
Tenex	2 / day		Swallow whole or CRUSH to put in food
Intuniv	1 / day	*	Swallow ONLY

* Take pill in the morning, or at night if causing drowsiness
It takes 2 to 3 weeks for medicine to reach beneficial level

Updated: 02/10/2011

doctor. Parents are consistently better informed about treatment options and have more realistic outcome expectations based on responses to a parent knowledge survey administered after the doctor-parent encounter. The card format is designed to provide a playful activity to encourage doctors to relinquish control of the learning agenda and spark a conversation about what matters most to parents. The card choice exercise allows parents to reveal what is most important to them. Initially, we saw that doctors did not allow parents to choose a card to discuss at the start of their interaction, thwarting the intended use of the cards. After developing a one-page pictorial 'card guide' and giving doctors one-on-one coaching on intended card use, 9 of the next 10 encounters included the doctor asking the parent to choose a card.

Figure 6. Sample medication card

CONCLUSION

During the project, the combined CCHMC medical/UC design team grew in trust and effectiveness in collaboration. Observations on our collaborative growth are organized following the phases through which the process unfolded. In Phase I it was important that the combined CCHMC/UC team adopt a shared goal and mutually agree that their combined expertise was needed. Obvious as it may seem, recognition by both teams that communication materials had the capacity to address the observed problem provided a foundation for extending initial trust; necessary time was taken for each team to educate the other in its respective domain knowledge and processes. On this foundation, the step-by-step building of trust was accomplished by faithful and rapid response in insignificant things building mutual trust for more substantive things. Also in Phase I, it was important for the design team to step up to the level of research rigor required by the medical team, as in acquiring human subjects research training. This meticulous attention to detail extended into Phases II and III in careful attention to design detail from color application and icon development to type size and word choices.

In Phases II and III, the design development and intervention phases, the team encountered different challenges. Though given different names by the design and medical domains, we found existing similarities in process: ethnographic research (design) and observation study (medicine); user-centered (design) and family-centered care (medicine); design evaluation (design) and evidence-based (medicine); user-test (design) and field trial (medicine). These shared processes facilitated our collaboration. On the other hand, broad and simultaneous exploration of multiple options, the joy of design, seemed foreign to the CCHMC medical team and perhaps tested their patience. In these phases the combined CCHMC/UC team functioned at times as a unified body, through evaluation of reports from the initial trials, during discussion of design alternatives, and evaluation and discussion of best approaches. At other times the teams

functioned independently: during design (design team active) and during implementation of interventions (medical team active). During these independent activities the less-active team still provided support services to the other. The design team made quick changes to files for testing, and the medical team reported what was happening to the design team. The mutual service is evidence of a smoothly functioning collaboration and continues to this day. Throughout, honest review of performance, willingness to abandon preconceptions, and open-minded consideration of options facilitated our collaboration.

Following Dr. Brinkman's presentation of the project at the CCHMC Place Outcomes Research Award Day, he was asked to present further to the CCHMC Research Committee of the Board of Trustees. These presentations fostered broad interest in further design-medical research collaborations. Dr. James Heubi, who co-directs the UC-CCHMC Center for Clinical and Translational Research has contacted Professor Zender and taken steps to develop a formal infrastructure to support continued collaboration.

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